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Open Data: Where to Start?

Exploring where to **deposit data**? Check out those marked with (†)

Generalist, Not for Profit Repositories - Least amount of curation support while meeting publisher criteria. A complete comparison chart is here: [10.5281/zenodo.3946719](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3946719)

- † **Zenodo** General-purpose repository. <https://zenodo.org/>
- † **Dryad** Supports minimal metadata curation. Charges a fee for deposit. <https://datadryad.org/>
- † **The Open Science Framework (OSF)** – Collaboration tool to support researchers throughout their entire project lifecycle. For citation, the digital object needs to be assigned a persistent identifier. <https://osf.io/>

Multidisciplinary, International Repositories - Moderate amount of curation support

- † **PANGAEA** – Digital data library and a data publisher for earth system science. <https://www.pangaea.de/>

Federated Portals - Full discipline-specific data curation support

- † **Ag Data Commons** – Centralized data catalog and repository for agricultural research data from the USDA. <https://agdatacommons.nal.usda.gov/>
- **Earthdata** – NASA's online portal for discovering, accessing, and visualizing Earth science data from NASA and partner agencies. <https://www.earthdata.nasa.gov/>
- **NIST Science Data Portal** – Publicly available datasets at NIST for Science, Engineering & Technology. <https://data.nist.gov/>
- **National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR)** – Earth system science datasets including meteorological, atmospheric, and oceanographic observations and model outputs. <https://ncar.ucar.edu/>
- † **NOAA Centers for Environmental Information (NCEI)** – Comprehensive gateway to NOAA's environmental data access tools and APIs. <https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/>
- **UN World Environment Situation Room** – Data platform created by the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) to provide data, information, and knowledge on global environmental conditions. <https://wesr.unep.org/>
- **USGS ScienceBase** – Digital repository providing access to scientific data products and resources from USGS programs. <https://www.sciencebase.gov/>

Cryosphere & Polar Data - Full discipline-specific data curation support

- † **National Snow and Ice Data Center (NSIDC)** – Cryospheric data and related geophysical data. <https://nsidc.org/>
- **UMN Polar Geospatial Center (PGC)** – Polar satellite imagery, digital elevation models, and historical maps. <https://www.pgc.umn.edu/>
- † **USAP-DC** – Datasets derived from The NSF Antarctic program. <https://www.usap-dc.org/>

Ocean & Marine Data - Full discipline-specific data curation support

- † **BCO-DMO** – Data and information from biological, chemical, and biogeochemical research conducted in coastal, marine, Great Lakes, and laboratory environments. <https://www.bco-dmo.org/>
- † **CCHDO** – High-quality hydrographic data from repeat hydrography programs (WOCE, GO-SHIP). <https://cchdo.ucsd.edu/>
- † **MGDS** – Marine geophysical and bathymetric data and metadata. <https://www.marine-geo.org/>

Geophysical, Geospatial & Geodetic Infrastructure - Full discipline-specific data curation support

- † **EarthChem** – Geochemical, geochronological and mineralogical data. <https://www.earthchem.org/>
- **EPA Geospatial Data** – Open geospatial datasets for environmental decision-making. <https://epa.gov/geospatial>
- **Geodetic Facility for the Advancement of Geoscience (GAGE)** – Geodetic data for measuring Earth's surface motion and deformation. <https://www.unavco.org/>
- † **OpenTopography** – High-resolution topographic data and tools. <https://opentopography.org/>
- † **Seismological Facility for the Advancement of Geoscience (SAGE)** – Seismological data, including ground motion, atmospheric, infrasonic, magnetotelluric, strain, hydrological, and hydroacoustic data. <https://www.iris.edu/>
- **Sedimentary Geochemistry and Paleoenvironments Project (SGP)** – Portal for sedimentary geochemical data with sample-level context (lithology, fossils, stratigraphy, geochronology, depositional environment). <https://sgp-search.io/>

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Ecological & Terrestrial Observations - **Full** discipline-specific data curation support

- † **Environmental Data Initiative (EDI)** – Ecological and environmental data, primarily from the Long Term Ecological Research (LTER) program. <https://edirepository.org/>
- † **ESS-DIVE** – Repository for environmental systems science data generated by DOE's Office of Science Biological and Environmental Research program (BER) <https://ess-dive.lbl.gov>
- † **HydroShare** – Collaborative environment for sharing hydrologic data and models. <https://www.hydroshare.org/>
- † **Knowledge Network for Biocomplexity (KNB)** – Repository for ecological and environmental data, primarily generated by National Center for Ecological Analysis and Synthesis (NCEAS) working groups. <https://knb.ecoinformatics.org/>
- † **Water Quality Portal** – Publicly available water quality data from the USGS National Water Information System (NWIS) and the EPA Water Quality Exchange (WQX) Data Warehouse. <https://www.waterqualitydata.us/>

Biological & Specimen Repositories - **Full** discipline-specific data curation support

- † **GenBank** – An annotated collection of all publicly available NIH DNA sequences. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank/>
- † **Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF)** – Biodiversity occurrence and observational data aggregator. <https://www.gbif.org/>
- **iDigBio** – Images and metadata for millions of biological specimens. <https://portal.idigbio.org/>
- † **Morphobank** – Repository with information on anatomy, physiology and behavior of species. <https://morphobank.org/>
- † **Movebank Data Repository** – Animal tracking and animal-borne sensor datasets. <https://datarepository.movebank.org/>
- † **Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS)** – Integrates and provides access to marine biodiversity occurrence records. <https://obis.org/>

Mineralogy Databases - **Full** discipline-specific data curation support

- **Mindat.org** – Crowdsourced, expert-curated mineralogy database with species, locality occurrences, photographs, and literature references. <https://www.mindat.org/>
- † **RRUFF Project** – Mineral database combining empirical analyses (spectra, structures, chemistry) with images and an open-access reference library. <https://rruff.info/>

Sample and Core Repositories - **Full** discipline-specific data curation support

- **International Ocean Discovery Program (IODP)** – Ocean sub-seafloor drilling cores samples and data. <https://iodp.org/>
- **NSF Ice Core Facility (NSF-ICF)** – Meteoric ice cores. <https://icecores.org/>
- **OSU Polar Rock Repository (PRR)** – Antarctic rock samples + metadata. <https://prr.osu.edu/>
- **Oregon State Marine and Geology Repository** – Marine cores, rock samples, and dredged material. <https://osu-mgr.org/>
- **Seafloor Samples Lab** – Over 14,000 archived marine geological samples. <https://www2.whoi.edu/site/seafloorsampleslab/>
- † **System for Earth and Extraterrestrial Sample Registration (SESAR)** – Global digital index of samples and specimens. <https://www.geosamples.org/>

Indigenous Knowledge & Knowledge Systems - **Full** discipline-specific data curation support

- † **Native Land Digital (NLD)** - Digital maps of Indigenous territories, languages, and treaties. <https://native-land.ca/>

Paleoscience Data - **Full** discipline-specific data curation support

- † **Neotoma Paleoecology Database** – Data resource that stores and shares fossil, paleoecological, and paleoenvironmental data. <http://neotomadb.org/>
- **NOAA Paleoclimatology** – World's largest archive of climate and paleoclimatology data, including tree rings, corals, ice cores. <https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/products/paleoclimatology>
- **Paleobiology Database (PBDB)** – Collection-based occurrence and taxonomic data for paleontology. <https://paleobiodb.org/>